

SPEECH COMMUNICATION AND TEXT

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada matn va kommunikatsiya jarayonlari o'zbek tili misolida yoritib berilgan. Unda nutq va matnning belgilari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: matn nazariyasi, matn lingvistikasi, axborot, so'zlovchi, tinglovchi, matn.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье на примере узбекского языка освещены текстовые и коммуникативные процессы. Это отражается на признаках речи и текста.

Ключевые слова: теория текста, лингвистика текста, информация, говорящий, слушатель, текст.

Annotation: The article highlights textual and communicative processes using the example of the Uzbek language. This is reflected in the characteristics of speech and text.

Key words: text theory, text linguistics, information, speaker, listener, text.

It is known that the participation of three main elements is a mandatory process in the emergence and occurrence of speech communication. These are the speaker, information and listener. (student). True, in modern speech communication, speech conditions, information channel (such as voice, writing, magnetic recording, telephone), the status, age and other characteristics of the members of the conversation, as well as various other non-scientific means, play an important role. important, even often decisive.

Linguistics naturally paid primary attention to the issue of linguistic expression and understanding of information, which is the main subject of "giving and receiving" between two parties (speaker, listener) in the process of communication. After all, the main goal of any communication is the "movement" of this information, and this "movement" is through language. That is why linguistics searched for the main and large unit of the same "information in motion", as a result of which speech was recognized as such a large unit for a long time.

In the words of the Polish linguist M.R. Maenova, the sentence that "Linguistics ends its observations where the speech ends" was considered an open truth until recently. Texts consisting of many sentences are excluded from the observations of this field of science, which is completely and completely bounded by the scope of grammar in the broad sense. In fact, if "linguistics ends its observations at the end of the sentence, i.e. considers only the sentence as a communicative unit, such linguistics will have a hard time entering the semantic-communicative essence of the sentence easily and fully. It is impossible to grasp the linguistic and logical core of any single sentence. Just as the meaning of any word acquires reality in a specific context, it is difficult to objectively assess the meaning of a sentence outside of its relationship with other sentences.

Let's pay attention to the example: in order to understand the content of the sentence Tourists will go to that city tomorrow, there should be some kind of sentence that was used (or can be used) before it, for example, a film about the historical monuments of Samarkand

was shown. It seems that the first sentence cannot be considered a completely independent communicative unit. So, the border of linguistics should not end here, but go beyond it. It is known that the interpretation of syntax only in the form of the doctrine of sentences (and word combinations) has been a pillar of this limit. However, it has been a long time since it was realized that looking at syntax as a "science of speech structure" sheds light on many problems.

Connected speech, integrated speech work, study of the text, i.e., the approach to the text in the form of sentence-period-larger fragment-integral whole began in ancient times - with Aristotle and his followers.

The development of the concept of text in Russian linguistics dates back to the 40s of the last century. In 1947, A.I. Belich, in his article on the classification of linguistic sciences, stated that in the grammatical description of language facts, a special place should be given to the entire chain of sentences that are connected on the basis of commonality of meaning and are manifested in the form of a certain syntactic-semantic integrity, and that the concept of "text" drew attention to the fact that it is of crucial importance for the occurrence of such sentences, and emphasized the feasibility of studying the interactions and connections in the chain of such sentences in the syntax department of linguistics¹.

The issue of large units of speech, i.e. "cooperation of sentences" was raised in German linguistics almost in these years, especially in 1949.

K.Boost, in his study of the most important tools that structurally form connections between sentences, such as lexical repetition, articles, pronouns, ellipsis, verb tenses, repeated conjunctions, interrogative words, writes: "It is drawn from one sentence to another the threads are so numerous and form such a dense web that one can speak of the intertwining of sentences, of their being woven as a single web, for each separate sentence is closely connected with the others²".

From the second half of the 60s of the last century, the direction called "text linguistics" entered a phase of rapid development. The text as a complete speech unit and its constituent elements, factors, and characteristics have been studied from different perspectives. A special, so to speak, huge "hype" has arisen around this industry. Even some experts considered text linguistics not a separate field of linguistics, but the foundation of linguistics in general. Periodicals and scientific collections on text linguistics were published in Western European countries, special scientific teams were formed, monographs were published, textbooks and even textbooks for schools were published.³

The text theory, the general formation and development of text linguistics were studied by Czech (representatives of the Prague Linguistic Circle), German, French, English, American, Dutch, Polish and other schools of linguistics, as well as Russian linguists. Researches in this direction in linguistics were thoroughly analyzed⁴.

The main rules on which recognition is based are summarized in the following groups:

1. The main unit of speech that expresses a complete idea is not a sentence, but a text; speech-thought is only a special case, a special type of text. The text is the highest unit of the syntactic level.

¹ Yanus E. Obzor polskix rabot po structure texta / Syntax texta. - M.: Nauka, 1979. - S. 335.

² S. Muhamedova, M. Saparniyozova. Text Linguistics. Tashkent, T-2011, -B. 12-14.

³ www. ziyonet.

⁴ www. ziyo net.

2. Concrete speech works - texts are based on the general principles of text composition; these principles concern the language system or language authority rather than the domain of speech. If these aspects are taken into account, then the text should be considered not only as a unit of speech, but also as a unit of language.⁵

Thus, a comprehensive study of the text as a speech and linguistic unit of a separate level requires the creation of a special science within linguistics - text linguistics. Text linguistics is formed and developing in this way. However, text linguistics in Uzbek linguistics has a lot of work and scientific research to be done. The consistent and planned implementation of tasks related to the development and improvement of communicative speech processes of the Uzbek language will give positive results in increasing the language and speech competence of the Uzbek people.

⁵ S. Muhamedova, M. Saparniyozova. Text Linguistics. Tashkent, T-2011, -B. 12-14.

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